

ICCAR 2023 PROGRAM

Session 1.1			04 NOVEMBER 2023 09:00-11:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-1	09:00-09:10	An investigation on existence and uniqueness results of a delay model of Mackey-Glass	Marwa Khemis	Algeria	Submission 329
Y-2	09:10-09:20	Entropy Generation and Natural Convection Flow of Hybrid Nanofluids (Cu-Al ₂ O ₃ /water) in square cavity	Nesrine Rachedi and Messaoud Guellal	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 330
Y-3	09:20-09:30	Enhancing Structural Resilience in Notched Plates through Functionally Graded Materials and Pre-Tensile Heat Treatment	Amir Slamene, Billel Hamza, Ilies Mrabet, Mohammed Yassine Mazari, Mohamed Mokhtari, Sadek Gouasmi, Habib Benzaama	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 331
Y-4	09:30-09:40	Numerical Prediction Technique for Gradual Structure Damage	Billel Hamza, Amir Slamene, Mohammed Yassine Mazari, Ilies Mrabet, Mohamed Mokhtari, Sadek Gouasmi, Habib Benzaama	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 332
Y-5	09:40-09:50	Simulation of a Solar water heater for an individual house	Embarek Nouredine, Azzouz Mahammed Chamseddine	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 334
Y-6	09:50-10:00	Remediation of Methyl Orange by Conducting Polymeric Composites	Muhammad Naveed Anjum, Mirza Nadeem Ahmad	Pakistan, Pakistan	Submission 336
Y-7	10:00-10:10	Wave Equation Inhomogenous Boundary	Hallouz Abdelhamid	Algeria	Submission 337
Y-8	10:10-10:20	Adsorption of Biebrich Scarlet Dye into Peels of vegetables and fruits as Adsorbents	Benkouachi Oumnia Rayane, Bougheuttoucha Abdallah	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 338
Y-9	10:20-10:30	Advanced Multiaxis Machining Strategies for 5-Axis CNC Optimization	ZIANI B., RAHOU M. and SEBAA F.	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 339
Y-10	10:30-10:40	Parameterized Programming Of NC Machining Instructions In a CAD Environment	ZIANI B., RAHOU M. and SEBAA F.	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 340

Session 1.2			04 NOVEMBER 2023 09:00 11:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-11	09:00-09:10	Influence Study Of Feed Speed On Roughness For AS13	HAOULEF B., RAHOU M. and SEBAA F.	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 341
Y-12	09:10-09:20	Enhancing the vibratory efficiency of composite beams strengthened with nano-structural elements through graphene platelet	Med Yassine Mazari, Besma Khouani, Ismail Bensaid and Ahmed Saimi	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 342
Y-13	09:20-09:30	Study and control of water quality in the Douera dam (Wilaya of Algiers)	N. Malki, S. Saidi, S. Hamil, S. Arab	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 343
Y-14	09:30-09:40	Modelling and simulation of Perovskite Solar Cells Based on Eco-Friendly Materials for High Efficiency	Selma RABHI, Abdelhadi Slami, Fatima Zohra SAIDOUNE, Karima DADDA, Yaacoub Ibrahim BOUDERBALA, Asmaa BOUZID and Mohamed BENATALLAH	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 345
Y-15	09:40-09:50	The vital role of calcium phosphate in medical applications	BENBOUDA Mouna, BOUDEMAGH Djalila, CHEBLI Derradji	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 347
Y-16	09:50-10:00	Adsorption with calcium phosphate and organic dyes: a powerful combination for environmental remediation	BENBOUDA Mouna, BOUDEMAGH Djalila, CHEBLI Derradji	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 348
Y-17	10:00-10:10	Antibacterial Activity Of Some Extracts From Warionia Saharæ (Asteraceae) Growth up In The South West Of Algeria	Mebarka Belboukhari	Algeria	Submission 350
Y-18	10:10-10:20	The influence of cement fineness on the mechanical strength of cement mortar	Tarek HADJI, Ahmed ATTIA, Salim GUETTALA, Taha Hocine DOUARA and Mostefa HANI	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 353
Y-19	10:20-10:30	Ag ₂ O-Bi ₂ O ₃ Catalyzed Photodegradation of Selected Pesticide under Irradiation of UV/Visible Light	Nimra Basharat, Muhammad Saeed and Saba Basharat	Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan	Submission 355
Y-20	10:30-10:40	The effect of thermal treatment on the mechanical strength at early age of an OPC mortar	Tarek HADJI, Ahmed ATTIA, Salim GUETTALA, Taha Hocine DOUARA and Mostefa HANI	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 356

Session 1.3			04 NOVEMBER 2023 10:00-12:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-21	10:00-10:10	Benilov et all operator and their discretization by the Fourier spectral collocation method	DERKAOUI Rafik	Algeria	Submission 357
Y-22	10:10-10:20	Structural Elucidation of E3-ligases and Tribbles to Explore their Involvement in Liver Cancer	Saba Basharat, Sajid Rashid and Sana Faraz	Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan	Submission 358
Y-23	10:20-10:30	Study of thermal and mechanical properties of poly (lactic acid)-hydroxyapatite composites	NedjmaTazibt, Mustapha Kaci, Nadjet Dehouche	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 359
Y-24	10:30-10:40	Smart polymers: from complex matter to stimuable behavior	Hadda BENACEUR, Fatma Zohra BENABID	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 360
Y-25	10:40-10:50	Adhesion and wetting of polymers: concept of surface modification	Hadda BENACEUR, Fatma Zohra BENABID	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 361
Y-26	10:50-11:00	A Theoretical Comparative Study of the 1,3-Dipolar Cycloaddition Reaction of some Alkenes with Nitrone	Boulanouar MESSAOUDI	Algeria	Submission 362
Y-27	11:00-11:10	Mineralization of the pharmaceutical pollutant ibuprofen by photocatalysis using gold nanoparticles loaded on mesoporous TiO2	Alaa Eddine ATTAR, Hanane CHAKER, Mustapha DJENNAS, Sophie FOURMENTIN	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 363
Y-28	11:10-11:20	Extreme Quantiles Estimator in the Context of Randomly Right-Censored Losses	Nour Elhouda Guesmia	Algeria	Submission 364
Y-29	11:20-11:30	The generalized eigenvalue problem and the computing the eigenvector from the Schur form of a matrix	MENAD Bendehiba	Algeria	Submission 365
Y-30	11:30-11:40	Study of the process of injected flow asymmetric twisting in a jet pump	Denys Panevnyk	Ukraine	Submission 370

Session 1.4			04 NOVEMBER 2023 10:00-12:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-31	10:00-10:10	Examining the Relationship between Dynamic Investment decisions and Technical Efficiency of Electricity Distribution Companies: A Case Study of Pakistan	Faisal Mehmood Mirza, Iqra Mushtaq	Pakistan, Pakistan	Submission 371
Y-32	10:10-10:20	Prediction of the silica fume effect on silicate formation using thermodynamic model	Tarek HADJI, Ahmed ATTIA, Salim GUETTALA, Taha Hocine DOUARA and Mostefa HANI	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 372
Y-33	10:20-10:30	A novel rectangular finite element formulation based on the strain approach for plate bending	Madjda CHENAFI, Messaoud BOUREZANE, Taqiyeddine ASSAS and Seyfeddine BENABID	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 373
Y-34	10:30-10:40	Study of the antibacterial and antioxidant activity of the "Punica granatum" plant from the M'sila region	Laib Nouri, Benyahia Azzedine, Melouki Azzedine, Deghfel Nadir	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 374
Y-35	10:40-10:50	Tax Evasion and Its Socioeconomic Consequences: A Comprehensive Review	Simeana Beshi, Driola Susuri	Kosovo, Kosovo	Submission 375
Y-36	10:50-11:00	Simulation of the choice of alkanolamine solvent (MDEA activated by piperazine and sulfolane) for the elimination of acid gases: an industrial case study in the Algerian northwest region	Rafik El Arslene DRA, Amira Ghislaine DRA, Maroua Khadra LAOUEDJ, Ibtissem DADI	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 376
Y-37	11:00-11:10	Decentralized Finance	Albina Hysaj	Albania	Submission 377
Y-38	11:10-11:20	Ni-Co/Al ₂ O ₃ nanocomposite coating with high resistance to corrosion and wear	Katia Nasri, Nadia Ait Ahmed, Hamida Issaadi and Nabila Aliouane	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 379
Y-39	11:20-11:30	Chemical Analysis of Groundwater Associated with Gypsiferous Soil Collapsibility Phenomeno	Farouk Rebiai, Abdelhamid Guettala	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 380
Y-40	11:30-11:40	Predisposition of Northwestern Ouled Djellel City to Gypsiferous Soil Collapsibility Phenomenon	Farouk Rebiai, Abdelhamid Guettala	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 381

Session 1.5			04 NOVEMBER 2023 11:00-13:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-41	11:00-11:10	Application of Electrical Resistivity Tomography to Assess Gypsiferous Soil Collapsibility Phenomenon	Farouk Rebiai, Abdelhamid Guettala	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 382
Y-42	11:11-11:20	Identification of Gypsiferous Sandstone Resulting from Chemical Weathering of Sandstone Associated with Collapsibility Phenomenon	Farouk Rebiai, Abdelhamid Guettala	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 383
Y-43	11:20-11:30	Identification of Sagging and Hogging Zones Beneath Buildings Associated with Collapsibility Phenomenon	Farouk Rebiai, Abdelhamid Guettala	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 384
Y-44	11:30-11:40	Limit of the core drilling method in the detection of the gypsiferous sandstone soil	Farouk Rebiai, Abdelhamid Guettala	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 385
Y-45	11:40-11:50	Building Damage Associated with Gypsiferous Soil Collapsibility Phenomenon	Farouk Rebiai, Abdelhamid Guettala	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 386
Y-46	11:50-12:00	Acroter Deformation Associated with Slope Movement Resulting from Hogging Zone Formation Due to Gypsiferous Soil Collapsibility Phenomenon	Farouk Rebiai, Abdelhamid Guettala	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 387
Y-47	12:00-12:10	Column Horizontal Cracking Associated with Slope Movement Resulting from Hogging Zone Formation Due to Gypsiferous Soil Collapsibility Phenomenon	Farouk Rebiai, Abdelhamid Guettala	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 388
Y-48	12:10-12:20	Plinth beam Cracking Associated with differential Movement Resulting from Hogging Zone Formation Due to Gypsiferous Soil Collapsibility Phenomenon	Farouk Rebiai, Abdelhamid Guettala	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 389
Y-49	12:20-12:30	Numerical Solutions for a Timoshenko Beam Subject to a Neutral Delay	Chabekh Meriem, Chougui Nadhir and Nacer Meriem	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 390
Y-50	12:30-12:40	Study of regularities of wear elements process of borehole jet pumps	Oleksandr Panevnyk	Ukraine	Submission 393

Session 1.6			04 NOVEMBER 2023 11:00-13:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-51	11:00-11:10	NiCoMn nanostructured powders used for wastewater treatment	DADDA Karima, DJERAD Souad, ALLEG Safia, DADDA Noureddine and HLIL El-Kébir	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 430
Y-52	11:11-11:20	New results on the input-to-output practical stability of time-varying infinite-dimensional systems	Hanen Damak	Tunisia	Submission 432
Y-53	11:20-11:30	Phytocenoses found in grassy mountain-meadow soils in the subalpine zone of Talish	Elshad Gurbanov, Sanubar Aslanova	Azerbaijan, Azerbaijan	Submission 433
Y-54	11:30-11:40	Adaptation of the genetic apparatus to extreme factors	Basti Asadova	Azerbaijan	Submission 436
Y-55	11:40-11:50	Transfer Learning based Fault Diagnosis of Bearings using Vibration Signals: Challenges and Future Perspectives	Chirag Mongia, Deepam Goyal and Shankar Sehgal	India, India, India	Submission 438
Y-56	11:50-12:00	AI-Driven Optimization of Battery Management for Enhanced EV Efficiency	Amel Ourici, Abderaouf Bahi	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 440
Y-57	12:00-12:10	Presssuremeter tests of cohesive soil: Evaluation of soil mechanical parameters	DENINE Sidali, ABBAS Yassine and ACHOUR Abderraouf	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 450
Y-58	12:10-12:20	AN OVERVIEW OF TOMATO LEAF CURL VIRUS: IMPACT, CHALLENGES, AND MANAGEMENT	Quazi Mohd. Imranul Haq	Oman	Submission 454
Y-59	12:20-12:30	Bi2O3-Co3O4 assisted photodegradation of selected pesticides in aqueous medium	Ujala Razzaq, Muhammad Saeed, Abdul Mannan	Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan	Submission 456
Y-60	12:30-12:40	IMPROVING CROP COMPETITIVE ABILITY OF FENNEL (FOENICULUM VULGARE MILL.) AGAINST WEEDS THROUGH INTEGRATION OF SOWING AND WEEDING TECHNIQUES	Safdar Ali	Pakistan	Submission 458

Session 1.7			04 NOVEMBER 2023 12:00-14:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-61	12:00-12:10	Halostachyseto belangerianae formation of the Shirvan plain. (Azerbaijan)	Sanubar Aslanova	Azerbaijan	Submission 459
Y-62	12:11-12:20	The Effects of Parenting Styles on Juvenile Delinquency	Brunilda Hoxhaj, Ergi Bardhollari	Albania, Albania	Submission 466
Y-63	12:20-12:30	Analyzing Game Strategies of the Don't Get Angry Board Game Using Computer Simulations	Ladislav Végh and Štefan Gubo	Slovakia, Slovakia	Submission 472
Y-64	12:30-12:40	The Impact of Monetary and Economic Policies on Risk Management in Banks	Thameur Oussama	Algeria	Submission 492
Y-65	12:40-12:50	A Review on Optimization of Continuous Stirred Tank Reactor Principal Parameters Treating Organic Substrates for Maximum Methane Production	Barkatullah Kandhro, Abdul Razaque Sahito and Sheeraz Ahmed Memon	Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan	Submission 497
Y-66	12:50-13:00	Software Quality Measurement: A Comprehensive Review	Ahmed F.Rashad, Shahla U. Umar	Iraq, Iraq	Submission 505
Y-67	13:00-13:10	Enhancing Chronic Kidney Disease Diagnosis using Machine Learning Classifiers: A Comparative Analysis	Abdul Majid, Muhammad Ismail, Fazal Muhammad, Jamal Hussain Arman, Bilal Khan	Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan	Submission 514
Y-68	13:10-13:20	Utilizing Decision Analysis and Game Theory in Resolving Conflicts in Albania	Robert Kosova, Daniela Qendraj Halidini, Evgjëni Xhafaj, Neime Gjikaj, Anna Maria Kosova	Albania, Albania, Albania, Albania, Albania	Submission 527
Y-69	13:20-13:30	Taguchi-GRA Optimization of Shielded Metal Arc Welding Parameters for High Strength Low Alloy Steel	Muhammad Saad Afzal, Aneela Wakeel, Muhammad Ali Nasir, Asad Yousaf	Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan	Submission 582
Y-70	13:30-13:40	Co-litigation in a civil procedure according to the Law on Civil Procedure Disputes	Argona Kuçi, Kastriote Vlahna, Dafina Vlahna	Kosovo, Kosovo, Kosovo	Submission 573

Session 1.8			04 NOVEMBER 2023 12:00-14:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-71	12:00-12:10	Budgetary organization at the central and local level according to legislation and practice in Kosovo	Dafina Vlahna	Kosovo	Submission 574
Y-72	12:11-12:20	General rules for measuring punishment according to the Criminal Code of Kosovo	Triumf Sadikaj	Kosovo	Submission 575
Y-73	12:20-12:30	Punishment for ongoing criminal offenses under the Criminal Code of Kosovo	Florim Salihu	Kosovo	Submission 576
Y-74	12:30-12:40	Taguchi-GRA Optimization of Shielded Metal Arc Welding Parameters for High Strength Low Alloy Steel	Muhammad Saad Afzal, Aneela Wakeel, Muhammad Ali Nasir, Asad Yousaf	Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan	Submission 582
Y-75	12:40-12:50	Photocatalytic Degradation of Selected Pesticide in the Presence of Bi ₂ O ₃ -Fe ₂ O ₃ Photocatalyst	Sadia Perveen, Muhammad Saeed and Nimra Basharat	Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan	Submission 602
Y-76	12:50-13:00	A Comprehensive Study on the Post-Graduation Journeys of MUET Alumni	Salman UI Mouzam Abbasi, Jawad Ahmed, Shiza Shah and Bhawani Shankar Chowdhry	Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan	Submission 608
Y-77	13:00-13:10	Echinacoside ameliorates hepatic fibrosis and tumor cell invasion in rats with hepatocellular carcinoma, exhibiting chemotherapeutic and hepatoprotective effects	Ajwan Z Albalawi, Areej S Alatawi, Shekha M al-atwi, Lama S Alhwyty, Mohammed M H Al-Gayyar	Saudi Arabia, Saudi Arabia, Saudi Arabia, Saudi Arabia, Saudi Arabia, Egypt	Submission 611
Y-78	13:10-13:20	Effects of cycloastragenol on Alzheimer's disease in rats by reducing oxidative stress, inflammation, and apoptosis	Wasayf A Almarwani, Khulud k Aljohani, Shahad A Alshehri, Kadi M Alharbi, MH Al-Gayyar	Saudi Arabia, Saudi Arabia, Saudi Arabia, Saudi Arabia, Saudi Arabia, Egypt	Submission 612
Y-79	13:20-13:30	Catalytic Conversion of Glycerol into Solketal as a Sustainable Fuel Additive using Mesoporous Tungstophosphoric Acid/MnCo ₂ O ₄ Catalyst	Wasim Akbar, Muhammad Farooq and Nimra Basharat	Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan	Submission 614
Y-80	13:30-13:40	Senonian deposits of the High Atlas Range of Marrakesh (Morocco): Sequence Stratigraphy and Geodynamic Evolution	ALGOUTI Ahmed, HADACH Fatiha and JDABA Naji	Morocco, Morocco, Morocco	Submission 623

Session 1.9			04 NOVEMBER 2023 13:00-15:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-81	12:00-12:10	Traveling Wave Solutions for a Degenerate Reaction-Diffusion Model	Samiha Djemai and Salim Mesbahi	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 391
Y-82	12:11-12:20	Wave Solutions of Reaction-Diffusion Systems in Population Dynamics	Samiha Djemai and Salim Mesbahi	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 392
Y-83	12:20-12:30	Analysis of coaxial heat exchanger and heat transfer fluid performance for the development of medium-deep geothermal energy	Tahar Souad, Zirari Mounir, Ykrelef Hichem, Saidoune Fatmazohra, Rabhi Selma and Kriby Saliha	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 394
Y-84	12:30-12:40	Application of Performance Based Seismic Design approach to Reinforced Concrete Building	Akram Khelaifia and Salah Guettala	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 397
Y-85	12:40-12:50	Assessment of Elastic Stiffness Factor in 2D Reinforced Concrete Frames with Varied Parameters	Akram Khelaifia, Meryem Ikram Adjeroud and Salah Guettala	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 398
Y-86	12:50-13:00	The Impact of Shear Wall Placement on Seismic Performance in Buildings	Akram Khelaifia, Ali Zine and Rachid Chebili	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 399
Y-87	13:00-13:10	Predictive Field-Oriented Control of Permanent Magnet Synchronous Motor with Space Vector Modulation Technique	Zorig Assam, Hamouda Noureddine and Babes Badreddine	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 400
Y-88	13:10-13:20	Assessment of the impact of infill walls layout on the seismic behavior of 3D reinforced concrete structures	Salah Guettala and Akram Khelaifia	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 404
Y-89	13:20-13:30	Analyzing Seismic Performance of Infill Walls: In-Plane and Out-of-Plane Behavior and Numerical Modeling	Salah Guettala and Akram Khelaifia	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 405
Y-90	13:30-13:40	Effect of stone sludge incorporation on cement brick production	Oday Jaradat, Mahmoud Shakarna, Asal Sirhan, Karima Gadri, Mohammed Khattab	Algeria, Palestine, Palestine, Algeria, Palestine	Submission 406

Session 1.10			04 NOVEMBER 2023 13:00-15:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-91	13:00-13:10	The effects of Ni doping on the Structural, Microstructural, and Optical properties of tin oxide films using PSP method	Roguai Sabrina, Djelloul Abdelkader	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 431
Y-92	13:11-13:20	The Effects of Crime and Deviation Detective of Socialization on the Behavior of Young Offenders, in University of Annaba-Algeria	Sahraoui Amara	Algeria	Submission 434
Y-93	13:20-13:30	Estimation of torsional effects of buildings using modal pushover analysis	Mahmoud Benkhelil, Mohamed Badaoui	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 452
Y-94	13:30-13:40	Knowledge of Nursing Students Towards Tele-nursing Care: A Cross-Sectional Study	Iaila Matrok, Raneem Faleh, Alanod Sultan, Shafa Rahil, Ayat M., Omar Masoud, Amara Bekhatroh Rashed	Saudi Arabia, Saudi Arabia, Saudi Arabia, Saudi Arabia, Saudi Arabia, Saudi Arabia	Submission 467
Y-95	13:40-13:50	Application of modal pushover analysis for 10-story asymmetric-plan building	Mahmoud Benkhelil	Algeria	Submission 486
Y-96	13:50-14:00	EXTRACURRICULAR ACTIVITIES – FACTORS FOR INTERETHNIC RELATIONS IN SCHOOLS	Besa Havziu, Diellza Kelmendi, Ardita Ceka, Afërdita Saliu	North Macedonia, North Macedonia, Kosovo, North Macedonia	Submission 578
Y-97	14:00-14:10	Difficulty of test by Fuzzy logic	Zhifka Muka, Armida Brakaj, Eriola Cenaj	Albania, Albania, Albania	Submission 587
Y-98	14:10-14:20	THE LEVEL OF E-COMMERCE ADOPTION IN SMES: THE CASE OF TIRANA, ALBANIA	Zhaneta Ndrejoni, Ledia Sula, Liljana Elmazi	Albania, Albania, Albania	Submission 603
Y-99	14:20-14:30	The impact of social media on consumer decision-making for choosing tourist destinations. The case of Albania	Ledia SULA, Zhaneta Ndrejoni, Liljana Elmazi	Albania, Albania, Albania	Submission 609
Y-100	14:30-14:40	Develop a model to analyse the roadside factors that affect the speed of vehicles on open-access highways.	Aziz Ur Rehman, Jamal Ahmed Khan	Pakistan, Pakistan	Submission 615

Session 1.11			04 NOVEMBER 2023 14:00-16:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-101	14:00-14:10	Determinants of international tourism in Albania: A panel data analysis	Visar Malaj, Najada Firza	Albania, Albania	Submission 616
Y-102	14:11-14:20	Non-homogeneous Poisson Process with polynomial function rate to predict road accidents: A case study in Albania	Denisa Kaçorri (Salillari), Albina Basholli and Luella Prifti	Albania, Albania, Albania	Submission 639
Y-103	14:20-14:30	The Impact of Corrosion Outer Defects on the Reliability of Hydrogen Pipeline Transport Systems	Abdelhakim MAIZIA, Ghania HABBAR, Abdelhamid GHOUAOULA, Abdelkader LOUZA, Abdelkader HOCINE, Abderrezak BEZAZI	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 504
Y-104	14:30-14:40	Real-Time Apple Disease Detection and Classification Using Hybrid CNN Model	Abdul Rafay, Muhammad Aqeel, Muhammad Iqbal, Ahmed Sohaib, Badarul Islam, Ahmed Zaheer	Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan	Submission 580
Y-105	14:40-14:50	Climate-Responsive Design of Vernacular Architecture in Hot-Dry Climates: Lessons from the South of Algeria	Ahmed Kaihoul and Efisio Pitzalis	Italy, Italy	Submission 592
Y-106	14:50-15:00	Innovations in Football Marketing Strategies for the 21st century, case of study Albanian Football Association	Ada Gashi	Albania	Submission 605
Y-107	15:00-15:10	UNRAVELING THE IMPACTS OF OCEAN PLASTIC POLLUTION AND STRATEGIES FOR EFFECTIVE MITIGATION	S. M. Rezaul Karim, Zulkefly Sulaiman, Saiful Ahmad Hamdani, Nayeem Asif, Wahidul Alam, Simul Bhuiya, Naina Islam	Malaysia, Malaysia, Malaysia, Bangladesh, Bangladesh, Bangladesh	Submission 640
Y-108	15:10-15:20	APPLICATION OF GIS AND REMOTE SENSING IN GEOTECHNICAL ENGINEERING	Haiz Muhammad Javed, Kashif Riaz	Pakistan, Pakistan	Submission 643
Y-109	15:20-15:30	Pozzolan (poz) effects on self-compacting concrete fresh properties	Rachid RABEHI, Mohammed OMRANE, Mohamed RABEHI, Ahmed Rafik BELAKHDAR, Mohamed Salah DIMIA and Mohamed AMIEUR	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 655
Y-110	15:30-15:40	Antimicrobial resistance of Salmonella spp. isolated from ground beef in Tirana market	Sonila Çoçoli, Egon Andoni and Tana Kika	Albania, Albania, Albania	Submission 657

Session 1.12			04 NOVEMBER 2023 14:00-16:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-111	14:00-14:10	Exploring Diverse Collapse Mechanisms in Infilled Frames: An Examination of Infill-Frame Interaction	Salah Guettala Akram Khelaifia	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 407
Y-112	14:11-14:20	Determining the performance point of reinforced concrete structures	Akram Khelaifia and Salah Guettala	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 408
Y-113	14:20-14:30	Seismic Performance Assessment through Pushover Analysis of Reinforced Concrete Buildings in Varied Seismic Zones	Akram Khelaifia and Salah Guettala	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 409
Y-114	14:30-14:40	Physico-chemical characterization of double lamellar hydroxides of the Mg Al-LDHs	Imene KECIR, Mokhtar BOUTAHALA	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 410
Y-115	14:40-14:50	Electrical performance analysis and optimization of Cu ₂ FeSnS ₄ /c-Si tandem solar device using AMPS-1D	Abdelhafid Mouhoub, Fahima Khaled and Abdessalem Bouloufa	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 411
Y-116	14:50-15:00	General stability of Lord Shulman thermoelastic system with porous damping and constat delay	Karek Widad, Bouzettouta Lamine and Lallouche Abdallah	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 412
Y-117	15:00-15:10	Optimization of spot-welding parameters	Besma Khouani, Ahmed Saimi and Ismail Bensaid	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 413
Y-118	15:10-15:20	Effect of pH on raw water treatment at El-Karma WWTP (Oran)	Khelladi Malika, Bekrentchir Khalida, Abaidia Meriem, Senouci Boulerial and Debab Abdelkader	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 414
Y-119	15:20-15:30	A comparative investigation of the elimination of methylene blue using three distinct natural and synthetic adsorbents	Imene KECIR, Mokhtar BOUTAHALA	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 415
Y-120	15:30-15:40	Investigation into how the molar ratio of HDL impacts the discoloration of water	Imene KECIR, Mokhtar BOUTAHALA	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 416

Session 1.13			04 NOVEMBER 2023 15:00-17:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-121	15:00-15:10	Synthesis, characterization, and application of magnesium ammonium chloride (MgAl-HDL) in the removal of red Congo	Imene KECIR, Mokhtar BOUTAHALA	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 417
Y-122	15:11-15:20	The Crucial Role Of Polytechnics And Community Colleges In Overcoming Challenges To Empower TVET In Malaysia	Mohd Daud Isa, Tengku Azman Tengku Mohd and Sharifah Nurulhuda Tuan Mohd Yasin	Malaysia, Malaysia, Malaysia	Submission 618
Y-123	15:20-15:30	The effect of material anisotropy on the energy absorption parameters of thin-walled structures under axial impact loading	Harkati Amine, Harkati El-Haddi and Bezazi Abderrezak	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 652
Y-124	15:30-15:40	The significance of Machine Learning in the field of Civil Infrastructure protection through image-based damage detection	Syed Taha Hassnain Haider, Dil Jan Khan and Muhammad Awais	Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan	Submission 581
Y-125	15:40-15:50	Inference of Sejahtera Academic Framework (SAF) principles in architecture pedagogy at DoA-KAED, IIUM	Nayeem Asif, Fadzidah Abdullah, Zeenat Begam Yusof, Aliyah Nur Zafirah Sanusi, Aida Kesuma Azmin and Noorizhar Ismail	Malaysia, Malaysia, Malaysia, Malaysia, Malaysia, Malaysia	Submission 653
Y-126	15:50-16:00	Control of a wind conversion chain based on PMSG integrating a vienna rectifier and Shunt Active Power Filters	SID AHMED FEKROUN, ABDELKADER MORSLI, ABDELHAFIDH MOUALDIA	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 664
Y-127	16:00-16:10	Eco-Conscious Tourism: A study on Green Turtle conservation measures at Pantai Kerachut, Penang	Nayeem Asif, Sarker Mohammad Rezaul Karim and Rafia Karim	Malaysia, Malaysia, Malaysia	Submission 667
Y-128	16:10-16:20	Timoshenko Beam Application in Dynamic Vibration Analysis for FGM Structural Rotor Using Finite Element Method P- Version	Ahmed Mezrag, Abdelkrim Boukhalfa	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 676
Y-129	16:20-16:30	Assessing the Mechanical Properties of Concrete with Recycled Asphalt Pavement (RAP) Aggregates	Mohammed Nadjib AZIEZ, Abderraouf Achour, Brahim Zitani, Charaf Abdekarim MOSBAH	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 465
Y-130	16:30-16:40				

Session 2.5			05 NOVEMBER 2023 13:00-15:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
T-17	13:00-13:10	2-Amino-6-substitübenzotiyazol Türevlerinin Ni(II) Komplekslerinin Antimikrobiyal ve Antifungal Aktivitelerinin İncelenmesi	Halil İlkimen, Cengiz Yenikaya, Aysel Gülbandır	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 366
T-18	13:10-13:20	2-Amino-6-substitübenzotiyazol Türevlerinin Cu(II) Komplekslerinin Antimikrobiyal ve Antifungal Aktivitelerinin İncelenmesi	Halil İlkimen, Cengiz Yenikaya, Aysel Gülbandır	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 367
T-19	13:20-13:30	2-Amino-5-substitüepiridin Türevleri ile 2-Metoksi-5-sulfamoyilbenzoik Asitin Proton Transfer Tuzlarının Sentezi, Karakterizasyonu, Antimikrobiyal ve Antifungal Aktivitelerinin İncelenmesi	Halil İlkimen, Aysel Gülbandır	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 368
T-20	13:30-13:40	2-Amino-6-substitüepiridin Türevleri ile 2-Metoksi-5-sulfamoyilbenzoik Asitin Proton Transfer Tuzlarının Sentezi, Karakterizasyonu, Antimikrobiyal ve Antifungal Aktivitelerinin İncelenmesi	Halil İlkimen, Aysel Gülbandır	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 369
T-21	13:40-13:50	Active Disturbance Rejection Control of a DC Motor with Raspberry Pi on Simulink External Mode	Erdem Ilten	Turkey	Submission 395
T-22	13:50-14:00	Fuzzy Logic Level Control of a Coupled Tank System with Raspberry Pi Application	Erdem Ilten, Haris Calgan and Metin Demirtas	Turkey	Submission 401
T-23	14:00-14:10	Classification Of Some Edible Submarine Organisms in The Mediterranean Region by Species Using Deep Learning Methods	Remzi GÜRFİDAN	Turkey	Submission 402
T-24	14:10-14:20	JEOLJİK FORMASYON TAKİBİNDE 2B ELEKTRİK ÖZDİRENÇ UYGULAMASI	Hasan Karaaslan, Ali Silahtar	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 422
T-25	14:20-14:30	IoT-Based Plant Irrigation Application with Mobile Control	Serkan Sökmen, Vedat Martın	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 424
T-26	14:30-14:40	Characterization and evaluation of phosphogypsum samples	Emine Sayılğan, Patrick Zhang	Turkey, USA	Submission 437

Session 2.6			05 NOVEMBER 2023 13:00-15:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
T-27	13:00-13:10	METAVERSE IN MEDICINE	Ziya Yıldız, Ahmet Ali SÜZEN	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 444
T-28	13:10-13:20	Boosting Predictive Power: Random Forest and Gradient Boosted Trees in Ensemble Learning	Bashar Alhajahmad, Musa Ataş	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 446
T-29	13:20-13:30	Investigation of Antibacterial Fabric Samples Coated With Zinc Oxide After Repeated Washing	Aslıhan KORUYUCU	Turkey	Submission 447
T-30	13:30-13:40	Üzüm Yapraklarında Görülen Hastalıkların Teşhisi için Derin Öğrenme Modellerinin Karşılaştırılması	Musa Ataş, Bashar Alhajahmad	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 448
T-31	13:40-13:50	MAKİNE ÖĞRENME METOTLARININ MANTI KALİTESİNİN BELİRLENMESİNDE KULLANILABİLİRLİĞİ	Serkan ÖRÜCÜ, Süleyman GÖKMEN	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 449
T-32	13:50-14:00	A Different Practice in Prenatal Care: Mellow Bumps	Ebru ERTAŞ, Feride ÇEVİK	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 451
T-33	14:00-14:10	Estimation of the Energy Amount of the Solar Energy System for the House Roof with Adaboost Algorithm	Yasemin Ayaz Atalan	Turkey	Submission 457
T-34	14:10-14:20	The Role of Explainable Artificial Intelligence in Diagnosing and Mitigating Potential Data Breach Risks in Healthcare	Ahmet Ali SÜZEN, Ziya YILDIZ	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 462
T-35	14:20-14:30	Spektrogram Tabanlı Derin Öğrenme ile Rakam Seslerinin Sınıflandırılması	M. Alptekin Engin, Latif Akçay	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 463
T-36	14:30-14:40	Utilization of Machine Learning to Predict Costs of Patients in the Emergency Department: Random Forest and Linear Regression Algorithms	Abdulkadir Atalan	Turkey	Submission 464

Session 2.7			05 NOVEMBER 2023 14:00-16:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
T-37	14:00-14:10	RAMADAN FASTING AND METABOLIC EFFECTS	Serap ÜNÜBOL AYPAK, Miray ACAR	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 468
T-38	14:10-14:20	Kakao (Theobroma cacao L.)'nun Beslenme Odaklı Antioksidan Özelliklerinin İncelenmesi	Muhammet DOĞAN	Turkey	Submission 469
T-39	14:20-14:30	Fonksiyonel Besin Olarak Böğürtlen (Rubus fruticosus L.): Besinsel Bileşimleri ve Antioksidan Özellikleri	Muhammet DOĞAN	Turkey	Submission 470
T-40	14:30-14:40	Particle board density and surface quality	Saadettin Murat Onat, Coşkun Kurşun and Orhan Kelleci	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 474
T-41	14:40-14:50	Feedback Control over Quantum Sensing Based on Bose-Einstein Condensate Trapped in Two-Dimensional Ring Potential	Sergey Borisenok	Turkey	Submission 476
T-42	14:50-15:00	Silver and GNS Substituted HA/Cs coatings on Additive Manufactured Co-Cr-Mo Alloys by Hydrothermal Method	Olcaç Mızrak, Oktay Yigit	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 484
T-43	15:00-15:10	k-Step Viterbi Algorithm with Discrete Control for Tracking an Unknown Number of Targets	Mehmet Kurucan, Mete Özbaltan	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 487
T-44	15:10-15:20	FOPID Control of a Coupled Tank System with Raspberry Pi Implementation	Metin Demirtas	Turkey	Submission 488
T-45	15:20-15:30	Controlling Complex Fractional Order Systems with the PID Controller	Bilal Şenol, Emre Avcuçu and Uğur Demiroğlu	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 489
T-46	15:30-15:40	Mekanik alaşımlamayla üretilmiş TiO ₂ ve Kaolin Takviyeli Al ₇₀ 75 Alaşımının Termal ve Mikroyapı Özelliklerinin İncelenmesi	Mehmet Emin DEMİR, Mustafa OKUMUŞ	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 494

Session 2.8			05 NOVEMBER 2023 14:00-16:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
T-47	14:00-14:10	St 52 Çeliğinin Hava Püskürtmeli Ortamda İşlenmesinde Kesme Sıcaklığı Analizi	Kübra Kaya, Üsame Ali Usca, Rüstem Binali, Mustafa Kuntoğlu	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 502
T-48	14:10-14:20	Üçgen Hava Kanallı Güneş Enerjili Hava Isıtıcısının Nümerik Analizi	Murat ÖZTÜRK, Erdem ÇİFTÇİ	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 506
T-49	14:20-14:30	Production of Aramid Based Composite Protective Equipment and Examination of Ballistic Performances	Özgür TEKASLAN, Ali ARI, Cebrail ÖLMEZ, Zehra SEVER	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 509
T-50	14:30-14:40	2018 İLKÖĞRETİM MATEMATİK ÖĞRETMENLİĞİ LİSANS PROGRAMININ DEĞERLENDİRİLMESİ	Ebubekir Akkoyunlu, Rabil Ayazoğlu	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 510
T-51	14:40-14:50	Evaluation of Internal Stability of The CEN-Standard Sand Based on Different Gradation Methods	Sadettin Topçu, Evren Seyrek	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 517
T-52	14:50-15:00	Mechanical Fastening Methods of Polymer-Based Composites	Ayça Demirer Kahraman, Fatih Kahraman	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 518
T-53	15:00-15:10	Makine Öğrenmesi Teknikleriyle Potansiyel Yetenek Avı	Merve Mirza Parıldar, Cemil Zalluhoğlu	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 519
T-54	15:10-15:20	Fluid Relationships of Young Individuals of the Digital Age Based on Distrust and Uncertainty	Serdar ÜNAL	Turkey	Submission 525
T-55	15:20-15:30	Encounters in Everyday Life: Culture of Distance and Loss of Sensitivity	Serdar ÜNAL	Turkey	Submission 526
T-56	15:30-15:40	Structure and Solution of Integral Equations with Fixed Kernels	Abdolvahap Ayaz, Münevver Tuz	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 532

Session 2.9			05 NOVEMBER 2023 15:00-17:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
T-57	15:00-15:10	Deep Geological Structure of the Malvern Rift South England from Aeromagnetic, Gravity and Deep Seismic Reflection Data	Abdullah Ateş, Ezgi Erbek-Kıran and Attila Aydemir	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 540
T-58	15:10-15:20	The Role of Financial Development, Globalization, Urbanization and Green Technological Innovation in Renewable Energy Consumption: Empirical Evidence in the Case of Turkey	Betül Altay Topcu, Sevgi Sümerli Sarıgül	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 541
T-59	15:20-15:30	Güneş Panellerinde Azimut ve Eğim Açılarını Kontrol Eden Hidrolik Devre Tasarımı ve Simülasyonu	Mahmut Can ŞENEL	Turkey	Submission 542
T-60	15:30-15:40	Demir Bükme Makinası Hidrolik Devre Tasarımı ve Simülasyonu	Mahmut Can ŞENEL	Turkey	Submission 543
T-61	15:40-15:50	Bayesyen Yaklaşım ile Türkiye’de Enflasyonu Etkileyen Temel Faktörlerin Belirlenmesi	Kadir Karagöz	Turkey	Submission 544
T-62	15:50-16:00	GASTRONOMİ VE DİJİTAL GÖÇEBELİK	Figen ŞİMŞEK	Turkey	Submission 545
T-63	16:00-16:10	Malzemelerin Manyetik Geçirgenlik Ölçümü	Dursun EKMEKÇİ, Emrah KAPLAN	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 550
T-64	16:10-16:20	Katot Materyali Sentezinde Kullanılan Başlangıç Materyallerinin Kristal Yapı ve Pil Performansına Etkileri	Erdoğan Öz	Turkey	Submission 552
T-65	16:20-16:30	Malzemelerin Manyetik Alan Dağılımı Ölçümü	Emrah Kaplan, Dursun Ekmekci	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 555
T-66	16:30-16:40	Clinical Importance of the Effect of Chromium Picolinate Supplementation on Serum Apelin, Resistin and Fetuin-A Levels in Obese Rats with Advanced Insulin	Ahmet Nedim KADİFECİ, İclal Geyikli ÇİMENÇİ, Ahmet Sarper BOZKURT, Omeed Akbar Ali ALİ	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 557

Session 2.10			05 NOVEMBER 2023 15:00-17:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
T-67	15:00-15:10	Genetik Tabanlı Metasezgisel Algoritmalar Vasıtasıyla Kademeli Ankastre Kiriş ve Betonarme Kiriş Optimizasyon Problemlerinin Minimizasyonu	Osman Tunca,e Serdar Carbas1	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 558
T-68	15:10-15:20	Üç Boyutlu Çelik Çerçeve Yapıların Optimum Boyutlandırma Tasarımı İçin Açgözlü Seçim İle Donatılan Buharlaşma Oranı Tabanlı Su Döngüsü Algoritması	Serdar Çarbaş, Osman Tunca	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 560
T-69	15:20-15:30	YAPAY ZEKÂ GELİŞMELERİ ve ChatGPT ÜZERİNE ETKİSİ	Kamil Aykotalp GÜNDÜZ	Turkey	Submission 562
T-70	15:30-15:40	Briyofitlerin Sucul Ekosistemlerde Biyomonitör Olarak Kullanımları	Özcan ŞİMŞEK, Kahraman SELVİ	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 570
T-71	15:40-15:50	SÜRDÜRÜLEBİLİR LOJİSTİK 4.0	Sibel ERİŞKAN	Turkey	Submission 583
T-72	15:50-16:00	EŞEK SÜTÜNÜN BESİN İÇERİĞİ ve İNSAN SAĞLIĞINA ETKİSİ	Gökтуğ Egemen GEZER, Seydi YIKMIŞ	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 585
T-73	16:00-16:10	MOF-5 Katkılı ve Katkısız TiO2 Fotoanot ile DSSC Üretimi ve Performansı	Esra KAYA, Arife GENÇER İMER	Turkey, Turkey	Mail Submission 1
T-74	16:10-16:20	MADEN İŞLETMELERİNE DEPREMLERİN ETKİLERİ	Gökhan KÜLEKÇİ	Turkey	Submission 495
T-75	16:20-16:30	Elmalı İlçesinin (Antalya) Farklı Zaman Ölçeklerinde Kuraklık Analizi	Erhan ŞENER	Turkey	Submission 515
T-76	16:30-16:40	Assessing Heavy Metal Pollution and Usage Characteristics of Surface Water Resources of Tavşanlı District (Kütahya, Turkey)	Şehnaz Şener and Erhan Şener	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 516

Session 2.11			05 NOVEMBER 2023 16:00-18:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
T-150	16:00-16:10	Fonksiyonel organik arayüzeyin hibrit aygıtın mikroelektronik özelliklerine etkisi	Harun Kıran, Arife Gencer Imer	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 548
T-151	16:10-16:20	Properties of the Middle Miocene Coal Seam II in the Çomu-Yanoğlan Coalfield within the Merzifon Fault Zone (İskilip-Çorum, Türkiye)	Rıza Görkem Oskay, Ali İhsan Karayığit and Enver Yılmaz	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 584
T-152	16:20-16:30	Trade Wars: The Cases of USA, Mexico, China	Serkan Şengül	Turkey	Submission 591
T-153	16:30-16:40	Unmanned Aerial Vehicle Anomaly Detection using Machine Learning Methods	Tansel Ozturk and Sengul Bayrak	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 598
T-154	16:40-16:50	Researching the Parameters That Impact Surface Quality in CNC Milling of HDPE Plate	Ömer ÇERLEK, Kubilay HAN, Adem TÜYLÜ	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 599
T-155	16:50-17:00	On Exponential Type Multiplicatively (s,P) -Functions	Serap Özcan	Turkey	Mail Submission 2
T-156	17:00-17:10	Parameterized Differential Transformation Method for Solving Initial and Boundary Value Problems	Oktay Sh. Mukhtarov, Merve Yücel and Kadriye Aydemir	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 533
T-157	17:10-17:20	Experimental Investigation Of The Structure Of Complex Aquabis(6-Bromopicolinato- κ^2 N,O)-Copper(II)	Ersin Acar, Emine Berrin Poyraz, Necmi Dege	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 561
T-158	17:20-17:30	Early Detection of Monkeypox Based on Visible Symptoms using Deep Learning	Ahmed Muhammed Kalo Hamdan, Dursun Ekmekci	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 594
T-159	17:30-17:40	Görüntü İşleme Yöntemiyle Akıllı Sera Tasarımı	Muhammed Asım Kesercioğlu, Yasin Akın, Ömer Çerlek	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 595

Session 2.12			05 NOVEMBER 2023 09:00-11:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
T-160	09:00-09:10	The Use of Simulation in Midwifery Clinical Education	Feride Çevik, Ebru Ertaş	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 597
T-161	09:10-09:20	Investigating Surface Quality Parameters in CNC Milling of UHMW-PE Sheet	Kubilay HAN, Adem TÜYLÜ, Muhammed Asım KESERCİOĞLU	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 601
T-162	09:20-09:30	Analyzing Surface Quality Factors in CNC Milling of Polypropylene Plates	Yasin AKIN, Ömer ÇERLEK , Kubilay HAN	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 604
T-163	09:30-09:40	Population-Based Vortex Search Optimization Algorithm for Solving Bin Packing Problem	Tahir SAĞ	Turkey	Submission 624
T-164	09:40-09:50	S235JR Metal Malzeme İçin Fiber Lazer Kesim Parametrelerinin Belirlenmesi	Yavuz Selim Ceran, Hüseyin Masunada, Gökhan Arıcı	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 632
T-165	09:50-10:00	Insights into the Crystal Structure, Hirshfeld Surface, and Void Analysis of a Malononitrile Derivative Compound	Sevgi Kansız and Necmi Dege	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 633
T-166	10:00-10:10	CVA6 ve Rocket Core İşlecilerinin Farklı Simetrik Şifreleme Algoritmaları Üzerinden Performans Kıyaslaması	Latif Akçay, Mustafa Alptekin Engin	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 634
T-167	10:10-10:20	Characterization of 4-Oxo-1,4-Dihydropyridine Compound with Ester Moiety Using DFT Calculations	Sevgi Kansız and Okan Şimşek	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 637
T-168	10:20-10:30	Bilgisayarlı Görmede Topluluk Öğrenimi (Ensemble Learning) Yaklaşımları	Musa Ataş, Bashar Alhajahmad	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 641
T-169	10:30-10:40	Lavanta (Lavandula angustifolia) ve Lavandin (Lavandula x intermedia Emeric Ex Loisel) Bitkilerinin Uçucu Yağ Özellikleri	Gıdık Betül, Yurtvermez Bayram	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 642

Session 2.13			05 NOVEMBER 2023 09:00-11:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
T-170	09:00-09:10	Carbon recycling from discarded batteries using an environmentally friendly method and its application in the removal of pollutants from water	Cihan Geçgel and Erdal Yabalak	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 644
T-171	09:10-09:20	Examining the Learning and Teaching Process with Classroom Activities in the Geometry Teaching Process	Fatma Cumhuri	Turkey	Submission 648
T-172	09:20-09:30	Kapı Kapanma Mekanizması Kinematik Analizi	Adem TÜYLÜ, Muhammed Asım KESERCİOĞLU, Yasin AKIN,	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 650
T-173	09:30-09:40	TÜRKİYE'DE ÜRETİLEN BİTKİSEL TOHUM YAĞLARI VE GASTRONOMİDEKİ YERİ	Muhammet ERBAY, Şeyma BOZDEMİR	Turkey, Turkey	Mail Submission 3
T-174	09:40-09:50	g-Metrik Uzaylarda İdeal Yakınsaklık	Saime KOLANCI, Mehmet GÜRDAL	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 500
T-175	09:50-10:00	Üçlü Diziler İçin Kuvvetli Lacunary I*-Yakınsaklık	Mehmet Gürdal, Saime Kolancı	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 503
T-176	10:00-10:10	G-Metrik Uzaylarda Bazı Yakınsaklık Kavramları	Saime KOLANCI, Mehmet GÜRDAL	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 520
T-177	10:10-10:20	EV TEKSTİLİ SEKTÖRÜNDE BİYOBOZUNABİLİRLİK ÇALIŞMALARI	Semiha EREN, Ceylan ATASOY	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 522
T-178	10:20-10:30	ALÜMİNYUM TREYLERDE KAYNAK TELİNİN İNCELENMESİ	Nihat OCAK, Buğra KAYA, Erhan DURU, Emin Emre GÖKTEPE	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 651
T-179	10:30-10:40	Multi Response Optimization of Process Parameters in the Extraction of Bioactive Components from Dill: Taguchi-MOORA Methodology	Mehmet Güldane, Hamza Bozkır	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 665

Session 2.14			05 NOVEMBER 2023 10:00-12:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
T-180	10:00-10:10	Does Renewable Energy Provide Economic Growth?: A VAR Model Application for the Netherlands	Burak Seyhan, Ziya Çağlar Yurttançıkılmaz	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 668
T-181	10:10-10:20	Kara Havuç Posasının HTC Yöntemi ile karbonizasyonu ve Hard Karbon Üretimi	Mesut KARTA, Tolga DEPCİ, Yunus ÖNAL	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 671
T-182	10:20-10:30	Mikrodalga Kurutucu ile Ispanağın Kurutulması	Mehmet GÜLDANE, Hamza BOZKIR	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 672
T-183	10:30-10:40	Patlıcan Dilimlerin Sıcaklık Kontrollü Mikrodalga Kurutucu ile Kurutulması	Hamza BOZKIR	Turkey	Submission 673
T-184	10:40-10:50	Hata Fonksiyonlarının Meta-Heuristik Algoritmalara Etkisi ve Transfer Fonksiyonu Optimizasyonu	Şehmus FİDAN	Turkey	Submission 674
T-185	10:50-11:00	Energy Saving Potentials in Fan Systems	Ergün KORKMAZ	Turkey	Submission 669
T-186	11:00-11:10	SEMI-EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION OF COMPOUND 1H,3H-BENZO[DE]ISOCHROMENE-1,3-DIONE	Emine Berrin Poyraz, Necmi Dege	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 625
T-187	11:10-11:20	Farklı Rakımlarda Yetiştirilen Ceviz Çeşitlerindeki Toplam Flavonoid Düzeylerinin İncelenmesi	Çağlar Mert AYDIN	Turkey	Submission 480
T-188	11:20-11:30	Liver cancer Properties of Extract of Atropa Belladonna L.	Burak TÜZÜN	Turkey	Mail Submission 4
T-189	11:30-11:40	Breast cancer Properties of Extract of Primula Veris Subsp	İlayda Bersu Yılmaz, Burak TÜZÜN	Turkey, Turkey	Mail Submission 5
T-190	11:40-11:50	Structural Performance Evaluation of RC Retaining Wall Strengthened with Counterfort	Sertaç Tuhta, Furkan Günday	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 620